

Predictive Value of Year 13 Performance on University GPA: A Study of Bachelor of Education Students

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ABSTRACT: This research looks at the academic performance of university students in Year 13 and relates it to their Grade Point Average (GPA). With this school year in mind, 1437 students' grades were considered. This study aims to determine how entering students' academic performance in Year 13 relates to their GPA-based success at university. This study used a mixed-methods approach to gather and examine data from university students' matched GPAs and Year 13 examination scores. From the population of one thousand nine hundred students, a sample size of one thousand four hundred thirty-seven students were selected randomly for the study. The factors impacting students' academic trajectories can be better understood and data interpreted using this multimodal approach. The possible correlations between Year 13 results and university GPAs are evaluated using regression models and correlation coefficients. The study also investigates how student demographics and study habits, which are not always related to academia, could have affected the links found. Pre-university academic achievement affects higher education outcomes; this is an ongoing discussion that the data adds to. Lastly, this research clarifies the intricate connection between university students' performance in Year 13 and their GPAs in later years. Improving the quality of higher education in Fiji and beyond may be possible.

Key words University Academic Performances, GPA (Grade Point Average), Students, Higher Education

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1. Introduction

The growing interest in institutional performance, as demonstrated by governments, trustees, stakeholders, and accreditation agencies, underscores the need to examine a critical issue in the higher education sector: the performance of students entering universities compared to the grades they ultimately achieve. This is particularly relevant given the increasing frequency with which students are returned for not meeting Minimum Entry Requirements (MER) across various fields of study. In this research, the focus is on teacher training programs, where such challenges have become notably prevalent. In the past decade, there has been a marked increase in the intensity of concern around the consequences of college education for students. Regional and program-specific accrediting

bodies' criteria and mission statements clarify that evidence of positive student outcomes is essential to today's certification requirements. High-quality education is provided at various levels to change people's consciousness, knowledge, and mental ability. Teachers and educators continually seek methods to improve student performance and assess their progress to measure the efficacy of their instruction. Analytic and data mining approaches have been developed to allow educators to examine enormous databases for patterns that represent their students' behaviour and learning (Arora & Saini, 2013).

The research university is the country's premier dual-sector university. We are specifically mandated to meet the educational needs of those in the community who require technical and trades certificates and diplomas (TVET) and those who wish to pursue undergraduate, post-graduate, and doctoral studies. University is one of the most significant contributions of teachers to the nation; most teachers in primary and secondary schools are teachers who went through university. The University admissions and scholarship eligibility frequently depend on marks scored in year 13 in Fiji. Students' universities are enrolled based on their performance in the last grade in secondary schools (year 13). The students' entry points are specific minimum education requirements for each study area. The students join the university with an average of 55% -90% marks in the year 13 examination for four subjects where a pass with 50 per cent marks in English is compulsory. The students go through a 3-year programme, which includes a practical mind theory class. The student must pass (pass marks is 50%) a total of 24 units in 3 years in a set structure to graduate as a teacher with a bachelor's degree. The bachelor's degree programmes are registered with the Fiji Higher Education Commission under FQF7 (Fiji Qualification Framework).

Institutions that provide teacher education play essential roles in the world of education; they have the power to alter the educational landscape and influence how future generations learn and acquire information. Education is sometimes referred to as the most excellent chance for building a more sustainable future, and teacher-education institutions are essential to change agents in reforming education and society to make such a future possible. Institutions for teacher education do more than train new teachers; they also update the knowledge and abilities of in-service teachers, develop curricula for teacher education, offer professional development for working teachers, contribute to textbooks, consult with neighbourhood schools, and frequently offer their expert advice to regional and national education bodies (UNESCO,2005). Teacher education generally consists of four components: improving the trainee teachers' general educational background, increasing their knowledge and understanding of the subjects they will teach, pedagogy and understanding of children and learning, and developing practical skills and competencies. The balance of these four factors varies greatly (Perraton, 2010). Furthermore, Teacher Education Institutions have the power to affect changes in educational systems that will impact future generations' knowledge and abilities. Teacher education institutes play a critical role in reforming education and society so that such a future can become a reality. Institutions for teacher education. The Ministry of Education ensures that all children, regardless of gender, ethnicity, or ethnic affiliation, have access to education. The government has developed educational programs such as formulating policies that will cater to the needs of students, improve the quality of relevant education, and make students less

reliant on the labour market but capable of venturing into self-employment after completing their course. The educational system is divided into Primary, Secondary, and higher education. The 8-year primary education is not obligatory, but it is provided free of charge to all school-age children. Mathematics, English, Health Science, Social Science, Elementary Science, Music, Computer, Physical Education, and Arts and Crafts are among the disciplines taught at this level.

Secondary education lasts five years, from Grade 9 to Grade 13. Mathematics, English, Fijian and Hindu languages, Technical Drawing, Woodwork, Metal Works, Home Economics, Computer, Chemistry, Physics, Biology, Agricultural Science, History, and Geography are the topics taught in secondary or high school.

2. Higher Education

The study would focus on the grades of the outgoing teachers from the university with the marks of the students enrolled since the general perception is that the students who scored high marks in secondary schools would score higher in terms of GPA at the university. Other factors determine the preface of students. Dayioğlu, M., & Türüt-Aşık (2007) researched whether there are any significant gender variations in academic performance among undergraduate students at Middle East Technical University. They found that, even though fewer female students were admitted to the university, they outperformed their male counterparts. Young and Fidler (2000) discovered that male students outperform girls on the SAT-M test due to differences in socioeconomic backgrounds, such as males coming from homes with a high income and educational attainment and taking more and higher. Stricker and Rock (1995) investigated the impact of personal and school factors on Graduate Record Exams (GRE). Personal qualities have a limited influence on scores, according to the research, and the education level of parents is the most beneficial predictor. They also discovered that school-related factors, such as institutional quality, influenced test performance. Urién (2003) states that personal qualities, family background, and study discipline influence students' academic achievement. According to Fertig and Schmidt (2002), there is a favourable association between pupils' linguistic abilities and having a working mother and father with a good education level and an intact family structure. Thus, the researchers would use secondary data to find if there is a significant difference in the intake marks of the students with a GPA.

3. Methodology

This retrospective quantitative cohort study used data from two cohorts over three years. The population for the study was one thousand nine hundred students taken from the university database of student records. From the population, one thousand three hundred and thirty-seven students were selected randomly for the study. This study will discuss the analytical modelling process, correlated metrics and concerns in the literature, and techniques for mitigating correlated metrics, describe the design of our case study, provide practical guidelines for future studies, discuss the threats to our study's validity, and draw conclusions. The data is examined using SPSS for t-test analysis to identify outcomes and

correlations. How the variables are related using correlation values will next be determined. A regression test is run to see if the results can be extrapolated to Fiji.

This study analysed the performance of students enrolling in BED Secondary and BED Primary by comparing the year 13 mark when the students enrolled with the GPA attained at graduation through a longitudinal study. The research was carried out using secondary data gathered from the university records over the last three years, where students will be selected randomly for Bed Primary and from different majors of Bed Secondary. The names and ID numbers of the students are not recorded; for the data, the researchers would need the marks of year 13, the discipline of the students, gender, and the GPA upon graduation. Once the data has been collected, it will be coded for gender, primary, secondary, and different disciplines so the values are placed during analysis. The Pre-approval for this study was received from the University Human Research Ethics Committee.

Table 1: Demographic representation

Sample population	Number	percentage
Female	907	63.12
Male	530	36.88
Bachelor of Education (Secondary)	1092	75.99
Bachelor of Education (Primary)	345	24.01

Table 1 and Figure 1 display the sample population distribution based on gender and education level. The sample consists of 907 females, representing 63.12% of the total, and 530 males, accounting for 36.88%. Regarding education, 75.99% (1092) hold a Bachelor of Education in Secondary, while 24.01% (345) possess a Bachelor of Education in Primary.

Figure 1: Demographic representation of the sample population

4. Result

Table 2: T-test results comparing year 13 marks for intake of students at the university for Bachelor of Education primary and secondary for male and female university students.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	f	sig
Y13_TOTAL Female Marks	907	259.72	29.805	0.990	1.391	0.238
Male	530	266.06	28.274	1.228		

The table above shows the statistical analysis results of the total marks by gender for Year 13. The statistics show that among the 907 females surveyed, the mean is 259.72, the standard deviation is 29.805, and the standard error mean is 0.990. An analysis of the data from 530 men reveals an average of 266.06, a standard deviation of 28.274, and a SEM of 1.228. There is a p-value of 0.238 and an F-statistic of 1.391.

It is evident from Table 2 that there is no significant difference between the marks of male and female students when doing intake for the Bachelor of Education Primary and Secondary at the University. Male students had a slightly higher mean, which is insignificant compared to female students. The minimum education requirement for the intake of students for the bachelor's program is a pass in year 13 with 220 marks and above. The high mean average indicates that the students are interested in teaching.

Table 3: T-test results comparing year 13 marks for intake of students at the university for Bachelor of education primary and secondary for male and female university students.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	f	Sig
GPA Female	907	2.599	0.777	0.026	0.307	0.579
Male	530	2.501	0.785	0.034		

The statistical analysis of gender-based GPA is presented in the table. A mean GPA of 2.599, a standard deviation of 0.777, and a standard error mean of 0.026 were recorded for the 907 females. There is a mean GPA of 2.501, a standard deviation of 0.785, and a standard error mean of 0.034 for the boys (n=530). A p-value of 0.579 indicates statistical significance, while the F-statistic is 0.307.

A paired-sample t-test was conducted to test the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between males and females concerning the GPA of Bachelor of Education primary and secondary at the university. The hypothesis has been accepted with a p-value of 0.570, greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference in the means. The females had a slightly higher mean than the males. It is not significant (See Table 3).

Table 4: t-test results comparing year 13 marks of the students doing Bachelor of Education (Secondary) and Bachelor of Education (Primary)

Program Name	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	f	Sig
Bachelor of Education (Secondary)	1092	265.6	28.318	0.857	6.155	0.013
Bachelor of Education (Primary)	345	250.8	29.949	1.612		

Data from a statistical study of final grades in Year 13 broken down by major is shown in the table. The average number of students enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (Secondary) programme is 265.6, with a standard deviation of 28.318 and an expected value of 0.857. There is a 250.8 mean, 29.949 standard deviation, and 1.612 standard error mean for the 345 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (Primary) programme. A p-value of 0.013 indicates statistical significance, and the F-statistic is 6.155.

It is evident from Table 4 that there is a significant difference in the marks of students joining the university for BED Primary and BED Secondary, as the obtained p-value was 0.013, which is less than the significance value of 0.05. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The students' higher marks in BED primary compared to BED secondary, which has a lesser Mean. The f-value of 6.55, far from 0, indicates more excellent evidence against the null hypothesis. This result means there is more excellent evidence of a significant difference when seeing the f-value.

Table 5: t-test results comparing year 13 marks of the students doing Bachelor of Education (Secondary) and Bachelor of Education (Primary)

Program Name		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	f	Sig
GPA	Bachelor of Education (Secondary)	1092	2.522	0.806	0.024	11.818	0.001
	Bachelor of Education (Primary)	345	2.693	0.683	0.037		

A statistical analysis of GPA is presented in the table, broken down by programme name. With a total of 1,092 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (Secondary) programme, the average GPA is 2.522, the standard deviation is 0.806, and the standard error mean is 0.024. With 345 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (Primary) programme, the average GPA is 2.693, the standard deviation is 0.683, and the standard error mean is 0.037. The F-statistic shows a significant level of 0.001, which is 11.818.

Table 5 indicates that the f-value is 11.818 and the p-value of .0001, which is significant at a 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Students doing Bed Primary have a higher mean GPA than those doing Bed Secondary. Since the population sample is large, the difference can be noticed significantly.

Table 6: Linear Correlation for Relationship between year 13 final examination marks as the entry point to the university to the student's GPA; the GPA indicates the students' performance.

Correlations		Year 13 Marks the entry point to the university	GPA
Y13_TOTAL Marks	Pearson Correlation	1	.082**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.0019

A correlation study between Grade Point Average and Final Grade in 13th Grade is shown in the table. Year 13 total marks and GPA have a slight positive link (Pearson correlation value = 0.082). There is a statistically significant association, as indicated by the significance (2-tailed) value of 0.0019.

Table 6 indicates the correlation coefficient of 0.082, which indicates a minimal positive linear link between Year 13's final examination grades and GPA. This indicates that there is a minor tendency for GPA to improve when Year 13 marks increase; however, the correlation between the two variables is not particularly strong. The p-value of 0.0019 is below the standard significance level of 0.05. This suggests that the correlation coefficient is statistically significant, indicating that the observed link is unlikely to have happened purely by chance. Based on these findings, it is evident that there is a statistically significant association between Year 13 marks and GPA. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the correlation is not strong. Additional variables beyond Year 13 grades are expected to significantly impact student's achievement at university, as evidenced by the low correlation coefficient.

Figure 2: Scatter Plot of GPA

The scatter plot depicts the relationship between Year 13 total marks (Y13_TOTAL) and GPA. Each blue dot represents a student's data point. The horizontal axis (X-axis) represents Year 13 total marks, while the vertical axis (Y-axis) represents GPA. The red line is the linear regression line with the equation $y = 1.99 + 2.18 \times 10^{-3}x$, indicating a slight positive slope. The R^2 value is 0.007, suggesting a very weak correlation between Year 13 total marks and GPA.

Figure 2 Box plots for the GPA of university students with the year 13 results. Examining the correlations of the university academic entry points and GPA in greater detail, the value of the correlation coefficients is 0.082, showing a positive weak correlation. This correlation is significant ($p = 0.0019$) at a 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The positive weak correlation shows that the year 13 marks of the student cannot determine the performance of the students at the university; students with low marks also score high in GPA. It depends on the effort put in by the students during their studies at the national university.

Table 7 model summary for the relationship between year 13 final examination marks as the entry point to the university to the student's GPA; the GPA indicates the student's performance.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.082 ^a	0.007	0.006	29.311
a. Predictors: (Constant), GPA				
b. Dependent Variable: Y13_TOTAL				

The table shows the regression analysis results that predicted the total marks for Year 13 (Y13_TOTAL) from the student's GPA. The correlation coefficient (R) of 0.082 shows a slight positive link. Year 13 total marks can only be explained by 0.7% of the variance in GPA, as indicated by the R Square value of 0.007. After adjusting for the number of predictors in the model, the Adjusted R Square value comes out at 0.006. The estimate has a standard error of 29.311. The dependent variable is the total grades from Year 13 (Y13_TOTAL), and the predictors are GPA (a constant).

Table 7 provides the R and R² values. The R-value represents the simple correlation and is 0.873 (the "R" Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation. The R² value (the "R Square" column) indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable, Price, can be explained by the independent variable, Income. 76.2% can be explained in this case, which is very large.

5. Discussion

It is customary to assess the quality of graduates based on their academic performance. The calibre of students a university enrolls is a factor that influences the quality of its graduates. Entry qualification is one indicator of a high-quality student. The study results indicated no substantial disparity in the admittance level of students from year 13 based on their grades at the institution. The study's findings align with previous studies by Adedeji (2001) and Zezekwa & Mudavanhu (2011), suggesting that students entering the University of Nairobi with high mean marks (C+ and above) in KCSE are more likely to achieve better academic performance. Studies by Lizzio, Wilson, and Simons (2002) suggest that a higher admission qualification score does not always correlate with better achievement in a term of study.

Studies conducted by Alias and Zain (2006) indicate a direct correlation between entry qualifications and academic success. Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) studied the correlation between students' initial grades and academic performance at Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. The results showed that there was no statistically significant relationship between students' entry grades and their overall academic achievement in science and mathematics courses ($r = -0.08$, $p > 0.01$). The researcher found that students' achievement at the university is influenced by their experiences within the college instructional environment, which should inspire learners for effective learning.

Furthermore, Chamberlin et al. (2023) conducted a study to investigate how Tertiary Entrance (TE) scores during students' years 11 and 12 of secondary education impact academic performance at the University of Griffith, Australia. A cohort of 64 students from the Faculty of Business Studies was selected. The results indicated a positive, although small, correlation ($\rho = .39$) between TE score and GPA, which was assessed on a scale ranging from 1 (poor) to 7 (high). The weak relationship may suggest that past performance does not determine present performance, perhaps due to cognitive development linked to maturity. Adedeji (2001) discovered a significant positive association ($\rho = .85$) between students' entrance scores and their academic achievement in the Faculty of Technology, University of Ibadan. Aderson, Benjamin, and Fuss (1994) discovered that students who scored between 777 and 999 in high school typically achieved a Grade Point Average above 3.0/4.0 in university.

6. Conclusion

This paper investigated the correlation between entry qualifications and academic success. The data indicate no statistically significant association between entry qualification and academic success. The correlations are not considered to be highly robust. Ultimately, the results of this study align with previous research suggesting a relationship between admission qualifications and academic achievement. Nevertheless, this is not the sole factor that can forecast performance. Entry qualifications alone may not reliably predict undergraduate performance. If applicants do not have outstanding average grades, other factors, including age, work experience, previous academic achievements, and involvement in extracurricular activities throughout secondary school, may play a significant role. Multiple studies have been conducted to identify and assess the factors that impact academic success. Newman-Ford et al. (2009) classified student elements as attitude, individual differences, physical health, readiness, and expectations. Home, cultural, parental influences and institutional aspects were discovered, including school type, population, discipline, personnel interactions, and admission and evaluation policies. Fenton-Smith, Humphreys, & Walkinshaw (2018). identified different aspects concerning instructors, instruction, and curriculum, including teacher-student interactions, classroom management approaches, curriculum content, teacher credentials, teaching methods, and instructional tools.

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Ethics approval and consent to participate: This study received approval from the University Human Research Ethics Committee. All participants provided written informed consent before participating voluntarily. They were also informed that they could withdraw from the study without any consequences.

Availability of data and materials: Data used in this study are available from the corresponding author on noble request.

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